

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO CHILDREN IN KINDERGARTEN

Sharifjonova Shodiya

Bachelor's degree student

Department of Foreign Language and Literature

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Tel: +998941766066

E-mail: sharifjonovashodiya@gmail.com

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Abstract: This article explores the significance and benefits of teaching languages, particularly English, to young children in kindergarten. It examines the cognitive, academic, and social advantages of early language acquisition, supported by research from prominent scholars in the field of linguistics and education. The article highlights how early exposure to English enhances cognitive flexibility, supports bilingualism, and fosters greater cultural awareness. It also discusses the long-term impact of early English learning on academic success and career opportunities, positioning English as a critical skill for navigating a globalized world. Through interactive and engaging teaching methods, children not only develop language proficiency but also improve creativity and problem-solving abilities. The article underscores the importance of introducing English at a young age to ensure a strong foundation for future learning and global communication.

Key words: early language learning, English language education, kindergarten teaching, cognitive development, bilingualism, language acquisition, academic success, global communication, social benefits of language learning, creativity and problem-solving.

In today's globalized world, English is increasingly seen as a vital skill for communication, education, and career advancement. Introducing English to children at an early age, particularly in kindergarten, offers numerous benefits that extend beyond language acquisition. Research from various scientists and educators emphasizes the critical importance of early language learning for cognitive, social, and academic growth. Below are several reasons why teaching English to young children is crucial, along with expert opinions and relevant studies.

1. Optimal Language Learning Age

- Maximizing the brain's adaptability:

Renowned linguist Noam Chomsky has long argued that the brain is especially receptive to language learning during the early years of life, a period often referred to as the "critical period" for language acquisition. According to Chomsky's theory of Universal Grammar, children are naturally predisposed to learn languages in their early years, and this ability declines with age. Early exposure to English during this period allows for more effective and natural language acquisition. For example, a study by Patricia K. Kuhl of the University of Washington (2011) highlights that infants exposed to two languages before six months are better at distinguishing between sounds in both languages, showing the benefits of bilingualism from an early age.

- Supporting bilingual development:

Studies by Ellen Bialystok, a cognitive neuroscientist at York University, have shown that bilingual children exhibit enhanced executive functions, such as better attention control, problem-solving skills, and multitasking abilities. Introducing English alongside a child's native language in kindergarten can thus support the development of bilingual skills and enhance overall cognitive flexibility.

2. Cognitive and Academic Growth

- Enhancing cognitive abilities:

Research by Viorica Marian at Northwestern University (2014) found that bilingual children demonstrate improved cognitive skills, including better memory, greater mental flexibility, and superior problem-solving abilities compared to their monolingual peers. This is due to the brain's need to manage and switch between languages, which strengthens cognitive control. For example, bilingual children often excel in tasks that require shifting attention between different sets of information, a skill that is highly valuable in academic settings.

- Laying the groundwork for academic success:

According to Jim Cummins, a leading figure in bilingual education, early exposure to a second language like English significantly benefits children academically, especially in subjects like science and mathematics, where English is often the medium of instruction in higher education. His research emphasizes that children who learn English early are more likely to succeed in international tests and be prepared for global opportunities.

3. Building Social and Cultural Competence

- Global communication:

Teaching English in kindergarten equips children with the skills to communicate with people from diverse cultural backgrounds. According to David Crystal, a linguist and expert on the English language, English is spoken by over 1.5 billion people globally and serves as the lingua franca in many international settings. Early exposure to English helps children understand and appreciate different cultures, fostering a sense of global citizenship. For instance, a study conducted by the British Council (2017) found that early exposure to English increases a child's ability to communicate with peers from different countries, enhancing cultural exchange and understanding.

- Boosting self-esteem:

Vivian Cook, a professor of applied linguistics at Newcastle University, argues that learning a second language like English early can improve children's self-confidence. Children who are proficient in English feel empowered to interact in wider social circles, which contributes to a positive self-image and social development.

4. Preparing for Future Careers

- Competitive advantage in the workforce:

In today's job market, English is often a requirement for professional success. According to a report from the World Economic Forum (2016), proficiency in English significantly improves employability prospects, particularly in global industries such as technology, finance, and international business. Teaching English from an early age helps children acquire a valuable skill that will serve them throughout their lives. For example, Ernst & Young found that nearly

40% of job applicants in multinational companies listed English proficiency as a key factor in hiring decisions.

- Access to global resources:

Children who learn English early have access to a wealth of educational resources, from books to online courses and academic articles, most of which are published in English. Research by Catherine Snow, a professor at Harvard University, confirms that children who are proficient in English have better access to advanced academic content, which aids in their intellectual growth and educational success.

5. Creating an Enjoyable Learning Experience

- Engaging, interactive methods:

Teaching English to young children is often fun and interactive, incorporating songs, games, and role-playing activities. James Paul Gee, a prominent researcher in literacy and learning, highlights that such playful approaches to learning make the language acquisition process more engaging and enjoyable for children. His work suggests that when children are exposed to English through creative and enjoyable activities, they are more likely to develop a positive attitude toward the language.

- Stimulating creativity:

According to Lev Vygotsky, a key figure in developmental psychology, learning through play stimulates cognitive development and fosters creativity. By engaging in English-language storytelling, role-playing, and problem-solving activities, children are not only learning the language but also expanding their imaginative and creative thinking abilities.

Introducing English at an early age, particularly in kindergarten, offers significant long-term benefits for children's cognitive, academic, and social development. Supported by the work of linguists and cognitive scientists such as Noam Chomsky, Ellen Bialystok, and Viorica Marian, it is clear that early exposure to English enhances cognitive abilities, supports bilingualism, and prepares children for future academic and career success. By prioritizing English education from a young age, we provide children with the tools they need to thrive in an increasingly interconnected and competitive world.

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